

Review Article

G-Force Dilemma: A Call for Standardization of PRF Preparation Protocols

Uday Hemant Barhate^{1,#}, Jitendra Sharan^{2,#,*}, Alok Kumar Sethi², Satya Prakash³¹Division of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Deformities, Center for Dental Education and Research, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi, India²Department of Dentistry, ³Department of Transfusion Medicine, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

Received: 8 August 2025

Accepted: 13 October 2025

Published online: 28 October 2025

Keywords: platelet-rich fibrin, relative centrifugal force, centrifugation protocols, leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin, standardization

Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF), a second-generation platelet concentrate, has been widely investigated for its potential in soft and hard tissue regeneration. The preparation of PRF matrices depends heavily on centrifugation parameters, particularly the relative centrifugal force (RCF). However, inconsistencies in reporting RCF values, variations in rotor dimensions, and differences in the calculation site (RCF-clot, RCF-min, or RCF-max) have resulted in significant confusion within the literature. This review aims to clarify the inconsistencies in reporting centrifugation forces for PRF preparation, highlight the biological consequences of varying RCF, and emphasize the need for standardization of protocols to improve reproducibility and clinical outcomes. A comprehensive review of studies from 2001 to 2024 was conducted, analysing centrifugation protocols used for leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) preparation. Data regarding RPM, RCF values, centrifugation times, and clot characteristics were extracted and compared. Emphasis was placed on the site of RCF calculation, device characteristics, and their influence on clot formation, cellular content, and growth factor release.

© (2025) Society for Biomaterials & Artificial Organs #20016725

Introduction

Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) is one of the blood concentrates obtained by centrifugation of peripheral blood. Since the introduction of Platelet Rich Fibrin (PRF), various health sciences fields have studied it extensively to facilitate soft and hard tissue regeneration, such as orthopedics, general surgery, burns and plastic surgery, dermatology, oral health sciences (orthodontics, oral and maxillofacial surgery, periodontics, endodontics, prosthetic implant surgery) to name a few (figure 1) [1,2]. One of the primary components of PRF matrices is platelets. The alpha-granules of platelets produce various growth factors, which are embedded into the fibrin matrices along with other inflammatory cells (figure 2). The interaction of platelets along with leukocytes further contributes to wound healing.

Relative centrifugal force (RCF) is an important factor affecting the nature of PRF matrices. Researchers have observed that changing the RCF values can obtain platelet concentrates with various

biological properties [3-5]. Choukroun et al have also evaluated the effect of RCF on the matrices of PRF. Reducing the RCF significantly increased the greater incorporation of leukocytes and platelets into the matrices of PRF [6].

However, there is significant inconsistency in the literature regarding the RCF values. Some of the studies have altered the original RCF values. Very few details regarding the rotor sizes, rotor angulation, and manufacturers of centrifugation devices were noted in the past studies [7]. Further, the confusion created in the field is the determination of the location of RCF. Few of the studies reported 'RCF clot', i.e., location at the formation of PRF clot [8-10], whereas few authors have utilized 'RCF-max', which is measured at the bottom of the centrifugation tubes [11-13]. On the other hand, initial studies by Choukroun et al. and Dohan et al. reported 'RCF min' values which are calculated at the upper portion of PRF tubes [14,15]. In a few of the studies, the location of the calculation of RCF was not mentioned. All the above-mentioned factors might lead to variations in the formation of PRF matrices. Therefore, this article aims to clarify these misunderstandings, and an agreement must be reached regarding more accurate means to report g-force values in future studies that investigate the various aspects of PRF.

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: jsbmds@gmail.com (Dr. Jitendra Sharan, Department of Dentistry, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India)

authors contributed equally

Figure 1: Application of PRF in various aspects of health sciences, and its specific applications in oral health sciences

Relative centrifugal force: Definition and calculation

The relative centrifugal force measures the gravitational force that a sample experiences during centrifugation. The goal of centrifugation of whole blood is to apply a relative force circularly to separate blood components according to their densities [7]. For decades, Centrifugation systems have been utilized successfully in most hospitals and research laboratories. Irrespective of the rotor size of the centrifugation device utilized and work conditions, the centrifugation system can be easily reproduced with the value of g-force. This is an internationally documented protocol to transmit working settings from one colleague to another for reproducibility [7].

However, these RCF values tend to change according to the angulation of the rotor radius, i.e, the distance between the rotor axis and the centrifugation tube. (Fig. 3, and 4) The RCF or gravity measurements depends on various parameters such as: the speed

(rotation/revolutions per minute, RPM), the rotor diameter and rotor angulation. Standard locations for the calculation of RCF for a centrifuge with a rotor with fixed angle are: the minimal r_{min} at the top inside (shortest distance to rotor), the clot r_{clot} in the middle of the fibrin clot (middle of the tube), and maximal RCF value r_{max} (at largest distance to rotor).

The farther the centrifugation tube is from the spinning axis, the more g-force it receives during rotation. The simplest example of this could be a tightly held child in the arms spinning at 1 rpm/second. In this case, the child would receive a certain amount of g-force. If the same child is holding onto a jump rope and rotated at the same speed, the child will experience greater velocity than in the latter case, hence the greater g-force/ RCF [16]. Therefore, the rpm value mentioned in the studies related to PRF in various research articles is utterly useless. The necessity of reporting the actual RCF value is to eliminate the effect of a change in the radius of the rotor of centrifugation devices, so that any operator in any part of the world could replicate the desirable properties of matrices.

The RCF can be calculated by the formula $RCF = 11.18 \times r \times (N/1000)^2$, where r is the radius from the rotor (center of rotation) to

Figure 2: Components of PRF: cell types, PRF matrix, and growth factors and bio-active molecules

Figure 3: Graphic representation of a centrifugation with the standard locations where the “relative centrifugal force” (RCF) or gravity (g) is measured. Reprinted with permission from [7], Miron RJ, et al. J Periodontol.90, (2019). ©2019, Wiley

Figure 4: Center of rotation of the centrifugation assembly. Courtesy: Beckman Coulter Life Sciences

the bottom of the centrifugation tube in millimeters (figure 4). N is the number of revolutions per minute. Therefore, there is a direct correlation between the radius and RCF. Internationally, the g-force is reported at the radius from the center of the rotor to the outer region of the bottom of the centrifugation tube (RCF-max) [17].

Various Studies Related to L-PRF

Most initial studies involving PC-O2 centrifuge have reported inaccurate rpm or RCF values. Many have transcribed these values, leading to further confusion and difficulty in the additional research. It was observed that despite using similar centrifugation devices and the same settings (RPM, time, and RCF), few studies have reported different RCFs. This is due to the variation of the location for measuring RCF. Even the original protocols have been modified

Table 1: Various studies and their protocols for the fabrication of L-PRF

Author	RPM	RCF	Time
1 Choukroun et al (2001) [18]	2700 rpm	750g	12 minutes
2 Choukroun et al (2006) [19]	2500 rpm	280g	10 minutes
3 Dohan et al (2006) [20]	3000 rpm	~400g	10 minutes
4 Simonpieri et al (2006) [21]	-	400g	12 minutes
5 Dohhan et al (2009) [22]	-	400g	12 minutes
6 Su et al(2009) [23]	2700 rpm	700g	12 minutes
7 Mazor et al (2009) [24]	-	400g	12 minutes
8 Dohan Ehrenfest et al (2010) [25]	3000 rpm	-	12 minutes
9 Simonpieri et al (2011) [26]	-	400g	12 minutes
10 Lekovic et al (2012) [27]	-	1000g	10 minutes
11 Kobayashi et al (2017) [28]	2700 rpm	708g	12 minutes
12 Pinto et al (2018) [9]	2700 rpm	~400g	12 minutes
13 Nizam et al (2018) [29]	-	400g	12 minutes
14 Meschi et al (2018) [17]	-	702g	
15 Cortellini et al (2018)[30]	2700 rpm	402g	3 minutes
16 Tehranchi et al (2018)[31]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
17 Nemtoi et al (2018)[32]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
18 Culhaoglu et al (2018)[33]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
19 Daugela et al (2018)[34]	2800 rpm	-	12 minutes
20 Bodhare et al (2019)[35]	3000 rpm	-	10 minutes
21 Caymaz et al (2019) [36]	3000 rpm	400g	10 minutes
22 Reyes Pacheco et al (2020) [37]	2700 rpm	-	14 minutes
25 Cho et al (2020)[38]		408g (RCF clot)	12 minutes
26 Palma et al (2020)[39]		? 400g	12 minutes
27 Sharma et al (2020)[40]	3000 rpm		10 minutes
28 Castro et al (2021)[41]	2700 rpm	408g clot	12 minutes
29 Aravena et al (2021)[42]	2700 rpm	708g	12 minutes
30 Barhate UH et al (2022)[43]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
31 Shruithi et al (2022)[44]	-	-	-
32 Wang et al (2022)[45]	-	408g	12 minutes
33 ElAmrousy et al (2022)[46]	2800 rpm	400g	12 minutes
34 Tadepalli et al (2022)[47]	2700 rpm	708g	12 minutes
35 Mubarak et al (2023)[48]	2700 rpm	408g	12 minutes
36 Santamaria et al (2023)[49]	2700 rpm	408g (RCF clot), 653g (RCF max)	12 minutes
37 Abad et al (2023)[50]	2700 rpm	408g	12 minutes
38 Gupta et al (2023)[51]	2700 rpm	? 400g	12 minutes
39 Darestani et al (2023)[52]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
40 Malzoni et al (2023)[53]	-	400g	-
41 Balarama et al (2023)[54]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
42 Mousavi et al (2024)[55]	2700 rpm	400g	12 minutes
43 Yavuz et al (2024)[56]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
44 Demirok et al (2024)[57]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
45 Omar et al (2024)[58]	2700 rpm	-	12 minutes
46 Coucke et al (2024)[59]	-	400g	12 minutes

by the pioneers for the betterment of formulations. Table 1 lists the number of studies and the protocols used to prepare PRF. Overall protocols of PRF formation vary between 2500-3000 rpm at the spin cycle of 10-12 minutes. Thankfully, a consensus was reached in 2019, and the pioneers appealed for the standardization of RCF.

Major Limitations of Reporting RCF Values and Scientific Inaccuracies

The L-PRF clot is produced by intraSpin devices located approximately at 50mm radius.^{9,30} However, based on the time of centrifugation, the site of formation of L-PRF clot varies.⁶⁰ Furthermore, the location of L-PRF clot varies from person to person depending upon the hematocrit levels of that person [60]. On average, 17% larger PRF clots were noted in females due to low haematocrit value. Furthermore, individuals living at high altitude have higher haematocrit values and therefore require higher centrifugation speed. Therefore, RCF at the bottom of the centrifugation tube would be more accurate than the RCF clot [43].

Biological Differences

The composition of the L-PRF clot depends upon the centrifugation machine, angulation of the rotor, tube composition, and the centrifugation machine's vibrations. L-PRF clots formed at low centrifugation speeds contain more platelets and leukocytes and have a higher amount of growth factors [61]. Miron et al (2020) in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) study also showed that the clots produced at lower centrifugation speeds (~200g) tend to have more equally distributed viable cells [61]. On contrary, the clots produced at higher RCF had denser fibrin matrix with cell distribution at the bottom of the fibrin clot. Wend et al (2017) investigated the growth factor release from PRF clots formed at low, medium, and higher relative centrifugation speeds [5]. They conclude that the growth factors released from low and medium-speed protocols were much higher than those produced at higher centrifugation speeds. Bagdadi et al also evaluated the growth factor release from PRF, A-PRF, and A-PRF+ and concluded that A-PRF+, prepared with a reduced RCF, displayed significantly higher growth factor release. Leukocyte and platelet distribution were also more uniform in A-PRF and A-PRF+ compared to PRF [12]. These studies state that by reducing the centrifugation duration and lowering the RCF, more leukocytes will remain in the fibrin matrix, possibly enhancing the release of growth factors [62]. The study's findings by Kubesch et al showed that PRF-high (719 g) induced a persistent and thick fibrin structure and inhibited cellular penetration of the host tissue. In contrast to PRF-high, PRF-medium (222 g) was more porous, had a much faster rate of in vivo vascularization, and contained significantly more human cells [4].

On the other hand, Castro et al. (2021) explored the mechanical properties, cellular content, and growth factors released after using various protocols to prepare various PRF matrices. Lower centrifugation speed decreases the tensile strength of the formed matrix clot; however, they did not find any significant difference among other mechanical properties, cellular content, and growth factor reserve. They concluded that RCF has a negligible impact on the characteristics of PRF clots[41]. Similarly compared to the lower 200 RCF ($5.7g \pm 0.95$), harvested 600 RCF membranes produced considerably larger L-PRF clots ($6.97g \pm 0.95$), with no significant differences between 600 and 400, or between 400 and 200 RCF. The platelet count of the L-PRF clot was unaffected by any of the three tested RCFs[62]. The weight and volume of liquid H-PRF grew in step with the RCF values. SEM also revealed that as RCF increases, the fibrin network becomes denser. According to CBC analysis,

more leukocytes and neutrophils were found in the 500 g group, and the 100 g group had the highest concentration of platelets and leukocytes. In addition, histological research indicates that cells produced by centrifuging 500 g of material for 8 minutes were spread most equally in liquid Horizontal-PRF (H-PRF)[63]. A direct impact on the product volume with an increase in RCF and time was noted by Arora et al, with an increase in time, platelet yields improved for each group of centrifugal force, with a force of 440 g at 10 minutes producing the highest yields, followed by 208 g at 20 minutes[64].

Therefore, further refined research, particularly clinical trials, is still required in this field to clarify ideas and develop new approaches.

Conclusion

The information available from the existing literature regarding using RPM and RCF to prepare L-PRF clots is confusing in nature. A slight change in the configuration of the centrifugation machine and tube influences the characteristics of L-PRF clots. To obtain consistent results, laboratory conditions should be replicated. RCF values and locations of calculations are also standardized to standardize the conditions, as RCF-clot varies with the centrifugation time. Therefore, the RCF at the end of centrifugation tubes (RCF-max) should be recorded to avoid this. RCF-max is not subjected to these variations. Further, a consensus must be reached, and a strict protocol must be followed regarding the RCF to prepare PRF-related clots. By following the 2019 consensus report, the production process of PRF will be universally similar. This will not only improve the level of care provided to the patient but also the predictability of the treatment.

References

1. Castro AB, Meschi N, Temmerman A, Pinto N et al. Regenerative potential of leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin. Part B: sinus floor elevation, alveolar ridge preservation and implant therapy. A systematic review. *J Clin Periodontol.*44,225-234(2017).
2. Ghanaati S, Herrera-Vizcaino C, Al-Maawi S, et al. Fifteen years of platelet rich fibrin in dentistry and oromaxillofacial surgery: How high is the level of scientific evidence? *J Oral Implantol.*, 44,471-492(2018).
3. Dohan DM, Pinto NR, Pereda A, Jiménez P, Corso MD, Kang BS et al. The impact of the centrifuge characteristics and centrifugation protocols on the cells, growth factors, and fibrin architecture of a leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) clot and membrane. *Platelets.*,29,171-184(2018).
4. Kubesch A, Barbeck M, Al-Maawi S, Orłowska A, Booms PF, Sader RA et al. A low-speed centrifugation concept leads to cell accumulation and vascularization of solid platelet-rich fibrin: an experimental study in vivo. *Platelets.*,30,329-340(2019).
5. Wend S, Kubesch A, Orłowska A, Al-Maawi S, Zender N, Dias A et al. Reduction of the relative centrifugal force influences cell number and growth factor release within injectable PRF-based matrices. *J Mater Sci Mater Med.* 2017;28:188-198.
6. Choukroun J, Ghanaati S. Reduction of relative centrifugation force within injectable platelet-rich-fibrin (PRF) concentrates advances patients' own inflammatory cells, platelets and growth factors: the first introduction to the low speed centrifugation concept. *Eur J Trauma Emerg Surg.*44,87-95(2018).
7. Miron RJ, Pinto NR, Quirynen M, Ghanaati S. Standardization of relative centrifugal forces in studies related to platelet-rich fibrin. *J Periodontol.*90,817-820(2019).
8. Anwandter A, Bohmann S, Nally M, Castro AB, et al. Dimensional changes of the post-extraction alveolar ridge, preserved with leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin: A clinical pilot study. *J Dent.*,52,23-29(2016).
9. Pinto NR, Ubilla M, Zamora Y, Del Rio V, et al. Leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) as a regenerative medicine strategy for the treatment of refractory leg ulcers: a prospective cohort study. *Platelets.*,29,468-475(2018).
10. Temmerman A, Vandessel J, Castro A, Jacobs R, et al. The use of leukocyte and platelet-rich fibrin in socket management and ridge preservation:

- a split-mouth, randomized, controlled clinical trial. *J Clin Periodontol*,43,990-999(2016).
11. Ghanaati S, Booms P, Orłowska A, Kubesch A, et al. Advanced platelet-rich fibrin: a new concept for cell-based tissue engineering by means of inflammatory cells. *J Oral Implantol*,40,679-689(2014).
 12. El Bagdadi K, Kubesch A, Yu X, Al-Maawi S, et al. Reduction of relative centrifugal forces increases growth factor release within solid platelet-rich-fibrin (PRF)-based matrices: a proof of concept of LSCC (low speed centrifugation concept). *Eur J Trauma Emerg Surg*,45,467-479(2019).
 13. Kobayashi E, Flückiger L, Fujioka-Kobayashi M, Sawada K, et al. Comparative release of growth factors from PRP, PRF, and advanced-PRF. *Clin Oral Investig*,20,2353-2360(2016).
 14. Choukroun J, Diss A, Simonpieri A, Girard MO, et al. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF): a second-generation platelet concentrate. Part IV: clinical effects on tissue healing. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*,101,56-60(2006).
 15. Dohan DM, Choukroun J, Diss A, Dohan SL, et al. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF): a second-generation platelet concentrate. Part I: technological concepts and evolution. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*,101,e37-44(2006).
 16. Miron RJ. Understanding Relative Centrifugal Force (G-Force). In: *Understanding platelet-rich fibrin*. 1st ed. Batavia: Quintessence Publishing; 2021. p. 71–82.
 17. Meschi N, Fieuws S, Vanhoenacker A, Srijbos O, et al. Root-end surgery with leucocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin and an occlusive membrane: a randomized controlled clinical trial on patients' quality of life. *Clin Oral Investig*,22,2401-2411(2018).
 18. Choukroun J, Adda F, Schoeffler C, Vervelle A. Une opportunité en parodontologie: le PRF. *Implantodontie*,42,55-62(2001).
 19. Choukroun J, Diss A, Simonpieri A, Girard MO, et al. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF): a second-generation platelet concentrate. Part V: histologic evaluations of PRF effects on bone allograft maturation in sinus lift. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*,101,299-303(2006).
 20. Dohan DM, Choukroun J, Diss A, Dohan SL, et al. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF): a second-generation platelet concentrate. Part III: leucocyte activation: a new feature for platelet concentrates? *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*,101,e51-55(2006).
 21. Simonpieri A, Del Corso M, Sammartino G, Dohan Ehrenfest DM. The relevance of Choukroun's platelet-rich fibrin and metronidazole during complex maxillary rehabilitations using bone allograft. Part I: a new grafting protocol. *Implant Dent*. 2009;18:102-11.
 22. Dohan DM, Diss A, Odin G, Doglioli P, et al. In vitro effects of Choukroun's PRF (platelet-rich fibrin) on human gingival fibroblasts, dermal prekeratinocytes, preadipocytes, and maxillofacial osteoblasts in primary cultures. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*,108,341-352(2009).
 23. Su CY, Kuo YP, Tseng YH, Su CH, et al. In vitro release of growth factors from platelet-rich fibrin (PRF): a proposal to optimize the clinical applications of PRF. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*,108,56-61(2009).
 24. Mazor Z, Horowitz RA, Del Corso M, Prasad HS, et al. Sinus floor augmentation with simultaneous implant placement using Choukroun's platelet-rich fibrin as the sole grafting material: a radiologic and histologic study at 6 months. *J Periodontol*,80,2056-2064(2009).
 25. Dohan DM, Del Corso M, Diss A, Mouhyi J, et al. Three-dimensional architecture and cell composition of a Choukroun's platelet-rich fibrin clot and membrane. *J Periodontol*,81,546-555(2010).
 26. Simonpieri A, Choukroun J, Del Corso M, Sammartino G, et al. Simultaneous sinus-lift and implantation using microthreaded implants and leucocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin as sole grafting material: a six-year experience. *Implant Dent*,20,2-12(2011).
 27. Lekovic V, Milinkovic I, Aleksic Z, Jankovic S, et al. Platelet-rich fibrin and bovine porous bone mineral vs. platelet-rich fibrin in the treatment of intrabony periodontal defects. *J Periodontol Res*,47,409-417(2012).
 28. Fujioka-Kobayashi M, Miron RJ, Hernandez M, Kandalam U, et al. Optimized platelet-rich fibrin with the low-speed concept: growth factor release, biocompatibility, and cellular response. *J Periodontol*,88,112-121(2017).
 29. Nizam N, Eren G, Akcalı A, Donos N. Maxillary sinus augmentation with leukocyte and platelet-rich fibrin and deproteinized bovine bone mineral: A split-mouth histological and histomorphometric study. *Clin Oral Implants Res*,29, 67-75(2018).
 30. Cortellini S, Castro AB, Temmerman A, Van Dessel J, et al. Leucocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin block for bone augmentation procedure: A proof-of-concept study. *J Clin Periodontol*,45,624-634(2018).
 31. Tehranchi A, Behnia H, Pourdanesh F, Behnia P, et al. The effect of autologous leukocyte platelet rich fibrin on the rate of orthodontic tooth movement: A prospective randomized clinical trial. *Eur J Dent*,12,350-357(2018).
 32. Nemtoi A, Sirghe A, Nemtoi A, Haba D. The effect of a plasma with platelet-rich fibrin in bone regeneration and on rate of orthodontic tooth movement in adolescents. *Rev Chim*,69,3727-3730(2018).
 33. Culhaoglu R, Taner L, Guler B. Evaluation of the effect of dose-dependent platelet-rich fibrin membrane on treatment of gingival recession: A randomized, controlled clinical trial. *J Appl Oral Sci*,26,1-10(2018).
 34. Daugela P, Grimuta V, Sakavicius D, Jonaitis J, Juodzbalsys G. Influence of leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) on the outcomes of impacted mandibular third molar removal surgery: A split-mouth randomized clinical trial. *Quintessence Int*,49,377-388(2018).
 35. Bodhare GH, Kolte AP, Kolte RA, Shirke PY. Clinical and radiographic evaluation and comparison of bioactive bone alloplast morsels when used alone and in combination with platelet-rich fibrin in the treatment of periodontal intrabony defects-A randomized controlled trial. *J Periodontol*,90,584-594(2019).
 36. Caymaz MG, Uyanik LO. Comparison of the effect of advanced platelet-rich fibrin and leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin on outcomes after removal of impacted mandibular third molar: A randomized split-mouth study. *Niger J Clin Pract*,22,546-552(2019).
 37. Reyes Pacheco AA, Collins JR, Contreras N, Lantigua A, et al. Distalization rate of maxillary canines in an alveolus filled with leukocyte-platelet-rich fibrin in adults: A randomized controlled clinical split-mouth trial. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop*,158,182-191(2020).
 38. Cho YS, Hwang KG, Jun SH, Tallarico M, et al. Radiologic comparative analysis between saline and platelet-rich fibrin filling after hydraulic transcresal sinus lifting without adjunctive bone graft: A randomized controlled trial. *Clin Oral Implants Res*,31,1087-1093(2020).
 39. Palma LF, Marcucci M, Remondes CM, Chambrone L. Leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin does not provide any additional benefit for tooth extraction in head and neck cancer patients post-radiotherapy: a randomized clinical trial. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal*,25,799-804(2020).
 40. Sharma A, Ingole S, Deshpande M, Ranadive P, et al. Influence of platelet-rich fibrin on wound healing and bone regeneration after tooth extraction: A clinical and radiographic study. *J Oral Biol Craniofac Res*,10,385-390(2020).
 41. Castro AB, Van Dessel J, Temmerman A, Jacobs R, et al. Effect of different platelet-rich fibrin matrices for ridge preservation in multiple tooth extractions: A split-mouth randomized controlled clinical trial. *J Clin Periodontol*,48,984-995(2021).
 42. Aravena PC, Sandoval SP, Pizarro FE, Simpson MI, et al. Leukocyte and platelet-Rich fibrin have same effect as blood clot in the 3-dimensional alveolar ridge preservation. A split-mouth randomized clinical trial. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg*,79,575-584(2021).
 43. Barhate UH, Duggal I, Mangaraj M, Sharan J, et al. Effects of autologous leukocyte-platelet rich fibrin (L-PRF) on the rate of maxillary canine retraction and various biomarkers in gingival crevicular fluid (GCF): A split mouth randomized controlled trial. *Int Orthod*,100681(2022).
 44. Shruthi TM, Shetty AD, Akash KS, Ahmed F, et al. Evaluation of effects of platelet-rich fibrin on treatment outcomes after impacted mandibular third molar surgery: A randomized controlled clinical study. *Natl J Maxillofac Surg*,13,46-51(2022).
 45. Miron R, Choukroun J, Ghanaati S. Controversies related to scientific report describing g-forces from studies on platelet-rich fibrin: Necessity for standardization of relative centrifugal force values. *Int J Growth Factors Stem Cells Dent*,1,80-89(2018).
 46. Miron RJ, Xu H, Chai J, Wang J, et al. Comparison of platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) produced using 3 commercially available centrifuges at both high (~ 700 g) and low (~ 200 g) relative centrifugation forces. *Clin Oral Investig*,24,1171-1182(2020).
 47. Tovar N, Benalcázar EB, Ramalho IS, Rodriguez CR, et al. Effects of relative centrifugation force on L-PRF: An in vivo submandibular bone defect regeneration study. *J Biomed Mater Res B Appl Biomater*,109,2237-2245(2021).
 48. Feng M, Wei Y, Wei H, Wang Y, et al. Effect of relative centrifugal force on the biological properties of liquid platelet-rich fibrin produced via horizontal centrifugation. *Clin Oral Investig*,27,399-409(2023).
 49. Arora S, Doda V, Kotwal U, Dogra M. Quantification of platelets and platelet derived growth factors from platelet-rich-plasma (PRP) prepared at different centrifugal force (g) and time. *Transfus Apher Sci*,54,103-110(2016).

50. Abad CE, Sanz-Sanchez I, Serrano V, Sanz Esporin J, et al. Efficacy of the application of leukocyte and platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) on alveolar ridge preservation: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res.*,25,592-604(2023).
51. Gupta S, Bhambri E, Sharma M, Shaikh MA, et al. Does leukocyte-platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) cause long-term acceleration in the rate of canine retraction? A split-mouth, two-arm parallel group, randomized control trial. *Dental Press J Orthod.*,28,e23288(2023).
52. Naeimi Darestani M, Asl Roosta H, Mosaddad SA, Yaghoubi S. The effect of leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin on the bone loss and primary stability of implants placed in posterior maxilla: a randomized clinical trial. *Int J Implant Dent.*,9,23(2023).
53. de Almeida Malzoni CM, Pichotano EC, Freitas de Paula LG, de Souza RV, et al. Combination of leukocyte and platelet-rich fibrin and demineralized bovine bone graft enhanced bone formation and healing after maxillary sinus augmentation: a randomized clinical trial. *Clin Oral Investig.*,27,5485-5498(2023).
54. Krishna VB, Duggal I, Sharan J, Mangaraj M, et al. Effect of leukocyte-platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) on the rate of orthodontic tooth movement and expression of various biomarkers in gingival crevicular fluid. *Clin Oral Investig.*,27,2311-2319(2023).
55. Mousavi Y, Paknejad M, Taheri M, Aslroosta H, et al. Comparison of histologic and radiographic changes of sockets grafted with L-PRF and sockets without intervention after tooth extraction. *Oral Maxillofac Surg.*,28,667-677(2024).
56. Yavuz A, Güngörmek HS, Kuru L, Doğan B. Treatment of multiple adjacent gingival recessions using leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin with coronally advanced flap: a 12-month split-mouth controlled randomized clinical trial. *Clin Oral Investig.*,28,291(2024).
57. Demirok SO, Eroglu CN, Koc A. Comprehensive analysis of bone tissue in extraction sockets of third molars after leukocyte and platelet-rich fibrin and photobiomodulation applications. *Clin Oral Investig.*,28,483(2024).
58. Omar YK, Rashidy MAE, Ahmed GB, Aboulela AG. Evaluation of leukocyte-platelet rich fibrin as an antibiotic slow-release biological device in the treatment of moderate periodontitis: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *BMC Oral Health.*,24,1530(2024).
59. Coucke B, De Vleeschouwer S, van Loon J, Van Calenbergh F, et al. Leukocyte- and platelet-rich fibrin in cranial surgery: a single-blinded, prospective, randomized controlled noninferiority trial. *J Neurosurg.*,141,500-508(2024).
60. Miron R, Choukroun J, Ghanaati S. Controversies related to scientific report describing g-forces from studies on platelet-rich fibrin: Necessity for standardization of relative centrifugal force values. *Int J Growth Factors Stem Cells Dent.*,1,80(2018).
61. Miron RJ, Xu H, Chai J, Wang J, et al. Comparison of platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) produced using 3 commercially available centrifuges at both high (~ 700 g) and low (~ 200 g) relative centrifugation forces. *Clin Oral Investig.*,24,1171-1182(2020).
62. Tovar N, Benalcázar Jalkh EB, Ramalho IS, Rodriguez Colon R, et al. Effects of relative centrifugation force on L-PRF: An in vivo submandibular boney defect regeneration study. *J Biomed Mater Res - Part B Appl Biomater.*,109,2237-2245(2021).
63. Feng M, Wei Y, Wei H, Wang Y, et al. Effect of relative centrifugal force on the biological properties of liquid platelet-rich fibrin produced via horizontal centrifugation. *Clin Oral Investig.*,27,399-409(2023).
64. Arora S, Doda V, Kotwal U, Dogra M. Quantification of platelets and platelet derived growth factors from platelet-rich-plasma (PRP) prepared at different centrifugal force (g) and time. *Transfus Apher Sci.*,54,103-110(2016).